

Host-guest complexes : spectroscopic and thermodynamic studies of crown ethers – dyes

V. Jayasree and S. N. Bhat*

Department of Chemistry, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong-793 022, India

E-mail : snbnehu@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 23 July 2001, revised 9 January 2003, accepted 31 January 2003

The interactions between hosts 18-crownether-6, 15-crownether-5 and 12-crownether-4 and guests 4-(*p*-*N,N*-dimethyl-*n*-amyl)styrylpyridinium bromide, APB, safranin T, acridine and azurene-A, azurene-B and azurene-C have been studied spectroscopically. Spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters indicate that the interaction between the crown ethers and the above dyes is weak. Generally 18-crownether-6 forms relatively stronger complexes with the dyes.

The term crown ethers are used to describe polyether containing repeating units $(x\text{-CH}_2\text{CH}_2)_n$ having only oxygen as hetero atoms¹. The ability to form complex with salts, e.g. solubilization of KMnO_4 in aromatic hydrocarbon, is facilitated by the addition of perhydroxydibenzo-18-crownether-6, and certain other compounds, is the most remarkable property of the cyclic polyethers². As there is no regular bond formation between crown ether and substrate, the substrate entrapment in crown ether is a dynamic process and there is an exchange between bound and free crown ether and substrate. The size, the cavity formed by the oxygen atom in the ring, the number and the kind of polar atoms in the host, the charge of the guest and the microenvironment of the guest contribute to the stability of the complexes^{3,4}. Elbasyouny *et al.*⁵ rightly pointed out that due to weak interaction between crown ether and neutral molecules and ions, reliable and reproducible results reported are very few⁶. Therefore, in order to understand the nature of interaction of crown ethers with organic molecules, it was thought worthwhile to carry out a systematic investigation of the interaction of crown ethers with organic neutral/cationic molecules under various conditions. In the present investigation, we have chosen 18-crownether-6, 15-crownether-5 and 12-crownether-4 as hosts and the guests used are spectral probes (4-*p*-*N,N*-dimethyl-*N*-amyl)styrylpyridinium bromide, APB, 3,7-diamino-2,8-dimethyl-5-phenylthiazinium chloride, acridine, azurene-A, azurene-B, azurene-C and safranin T, which are known to exhibit absorption spectra in the visible region.

Results and discussion

Crown ether complexes of APB :

The electronic absorption spectrum of 4-(*p*-*N,N*-dimethyl-*N*-amyl)styrylpyridinium bromide, APB, consists of two peaks at 267 ($\epsilon = 8390 \pm 95$) and other at 453 nm ($\epsilon = 22537 \pm 120 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (lit. 450 nm). With the addition of 18-crownether-6, the 453 nm band of APB shifts to 456 nm, which is concentration-dependent. From the difference between the absorbances of APB with and without 18-crownether-6, we could locate a new band with absorbance maximum ~ 330 nm and this new band can be attributed to the 18-crownether-6-APB complex (host-guest). The decrease in absorbance of APB in the visible region can be due to the decrease in concentration of free APB, as some of the APB molecules are complexed with 18-crownether-6 molecules forming the host-guest systems and this complex absorbs at ~ 330 nm. It can be seen from the figure (not shown) that there is an isosbestic point at $\lambda_{\text{iso}} = 365 \pm 1$ nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 5764 \pm 114 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and ϵ_{iso} slightly decreases with the increase in temperature, whereas λ_{iso} is temperature-independent. So, the presence of an isosbestic point as well as the appearance of a new band ($\lambda_{\text{ct}} = 330$ nm) whose intensity is reversed with the restoration of temperature, indicate that 18-crownether-6 interacts with APB to form a host-guest complex. APB, a cationic dye (with π electrons), can act as a weak electron-acceptor whereas 18-crownether-6 (diameter 2.6–3.2 Å) having 6 oxygen atoms in the ring acts as (weak) electron-donor towards APB. For forming a complex of maximum stability, the host should have an optimum polyether ring size, so that the guest can properly fit encapsulated into the host cavity. But from the geometry of APB, it appears that APB may not fit properly into the cavity of 18-crownether-6, as the presence of methyl groups in APB may not allow even the formation of

*Present address : Chemistry P. G. Department, V. V. Puram Science College, V. V. Puram, Bangalore-560 004, India.

proper sandwich type complexes. However, a complex can form even if the 'fit' is not the best, by forming a sandwich type complex, consisting of guest in between two molecules of polyether. The stoichiometry of the complex was found to be 1 : 1. Equilibrium constant for the formation of crown ether APB complexes was determined using the B-H equation⁷ as well as on Nagakura's⁸ approach and the results are summarized in Table 1. The equilibrium constant calculated using both methods was found to be nearly the same, i.e.

plotted against $1/T$. The ΔH° thus obtained is small and ΔS° is small and negative which indicates that the interaction between 18-crownether-6 and APB is weak. Here it may be noted that the enthalpy changes measured calorimetrically on metallic cations are also very small⁴. From the thermodynamic parameters, it appears that 18-crownether-6-APB complex formation is enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled. The negative entropy shows that the complex is more rigid.

Table 1. Spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters of crown ether complexes*

Host	Parameter	Guests					
		APB	Safranin-F	Aeridine	Azurene-A	Azurene-B	Azurene-C
18-Crownether-6	λ_{CT} , nm	330	524	404	634	636	618
	ϵ_{CT} , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	9090 ± 132	6666 ± 175	3846 ± 145	23809 ± 138	1538 ± 142	4347 ± 102
	K_{298} , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$33 (35) \pm 2$	$201 (209) \pm 10$	$94 (95) \pm 2$	$157 (164) \pm 6$	$105 (108) \pm 7$	$245 (270) \pm 11$
	ΔH° , kJ mol^{-1}	13.30 (13.3)	13.30 (13.1)	35.75 (36.58)	29.93 (29.09)	27.44 (27.4)	20.78 (20.70)
	ΔG° , kJ mol^{-1}	3.76 (3.85)	5.69 (5.69)	4.90 (4.90)	5.43 (5.47)	5.03 (5.03)	5.92 (6.02)
	ΔS° , kJ mol^{-1}	0.032	0.029 (0.026)	0.104 (0.106)	0.082 (0.079)	0.075 (0.075)	0.049 (0.049)
15-Crownether-5	λ_{CT} , nm	315	534	405	637	662	620
	ϵ_{CT} , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	5000 ± 123	5000 ± 150	5000 ± 121	2000 ± 67	3333 ± 117	8333 ± 112
	K_{298} , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$20.8 (20.8) \pm 2$	$154 (160) \pm 6$	$61 (64) \pm 11$	$125 (132) \pm 4$	$95 (104) \pm 3$	$156 (164) \pm 6$
	ΔH° , kJ mol^{-1}	13.30 (13.30)	14.13 (14.13)	26.6 (24.9)	33.25 (34.04)	28.26 (27.4)	33.25 (33.25)
	ΔG° , kJ mol^{-1}	3.24 (3.24)	5.42 (5.42)	4.24 (4.47)	5.19 (5.25)	4.89 (4.95)	5.42 (5.47)
	ΔS° , kJ mol^{-1}	0.034 (0.034)	0.029 (0.029)	0.074 (0.09)	0.094 (0.096)	0.078 (0.082)	0.093 (0.092)
12-Crownether-4	λ_{CT} , nm	310	528	405			
	ϵ_{CT} , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	8333 ± 113	6666 ± 148	5000 ± 138			
	K_{298} , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$12.30 (13) \pm 1$	$108 (104) \pm 5$	$36 (38) \pm 2$			
	ΔH° , kJ mol^{-1}	13.30 (13.34)	14.96 (14.96)	34.21 (35.70)			
	ΔG° , kJ mol^{-1}	2.74 (2.74)	5.03 (4.99)	3.85 (3.91)			
	ΔS° , kJ mol^{-1}	0.032 (0.035)	0.033 (0.033)	0.102 (0.107)			

*Value in parenthesis refer to that obtained following Nagakura's procedure (Ref. 8). The data on 12-crown-4-azurenes could not be obtained due to practical constraints.

Error limits ± 1 nm.

$33 \pm 3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ and $\epsilon_{CT} = 9090 \pm 132 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. Here it may be noted that the frequency of charge transfer band is primary datum which is reasonably certain, whereas the equilibrium constant, molar extinction coefficient, enthalpy and entropy changes are secondary data-derived data, have higher uncertainties. In the case of weak complexes, like the present one, it is difficult to obtain the reliable value of K , from the K_ϵ values (as uncertainty is high in the separation of K and ϵ from K_ϵ). So, in order to obtain ΔH° , assuming that ϵ is independent of temperature, $\log K_\epsilon$ is

15-Crownether-5-APB complex :

On the addition of 15-crownether-5 to APB, the absorption of 453 nm band of APB slightly decreases and shifts to 456 nm whereas the absorbance near UV region increases with λ_{max} at 315 nm. An isosbestic point at 365 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 6032 \pm 118 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) (which is temperature-independent) is obtained. The presence of an isosbestic point and the appearance of a new band (whose intensity is resorted when the temperature is brought back to the initial temperature) indicate that 15-crownether-5 interacts with

APB to form a reversible complex. The calculated association constant and molar extinction coefficient of the complex are given in Table 1. The free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes for the complexation which are small and negative indicate that 15-crownether-5 and APB interact with each other and the complex formed is weak.

12-Crownether-4-APB-complex :

On the addition of 12-crownether-4 to APB, the absorbance of APB, in visible region ($\lambda_{\max}$ 453 nm) decreases and the decrease is followed by a simultaneous increase in the absorbance at shorter wavelength. The new band ($\lambda_{\max}$ = 310 nm) can be ascribed to the 12-crown-4-APB complex. With the addition of various amounts of 12-crownether-4 to the same concentration of APB, the spectra intersect at 365 nm (i.e. an isosbestic point is obtained). The λ_{iso} and ϵ_{iso} are practically independent of temperature. The calculated equilibrium constants and molar extinction coefficients of the complex are included in Table 1. The free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes for the complexation are $-2.74 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $13.30 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $0.032 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. This complex formation seems to be enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled.

The diameters of cavities of crownethers vary in the order : 18-crownether-6 (2.6–3.2 Å) > 15-crownether-5 (1.7–2.2 Å) > 12-crownether-4 (~1 Å)¹. The present investigation reveals that the crownethers do interact with APB and the stability/strength of interaction of the host-guest systems (of crownether-APB) vary in the order : 18-crownether-6-APB > 15-crownether-5-APB > 12-crownether-4-APB. The binding constants and free energies of complexation seem to be controlled by the number of binding sites. So from these data, one is tempted to infer that the cationic dye, APB, like alkaline metallic cations, may be encapsulated into the cavity of crownethers and the crownethers may hold APB molecules by electrostatic/van der Waals attraction. Of course with the limited experimental data, we do not intend to generalize that the APB molecules may be having such geometry/diameter that can properly fit into the cavity of 18-crownether-6 more favourable compared to that of 15-crownether-5 or 12-crownether-4.

18-Crownether-6-acridine complex :

Acridine has three absorption bands, namely, 338 ($\epsilon = 5736 \pm 53$), 347 ($\epsilon = 6492 \pm 38$) and 355 nm ($\epsilon = 10395 \pm 175 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). With the addition of crownether, the absorbance of acridine between 310 and 450 nm has increased. From the difference between the absorbance of acridine with and without crownether, a new band with $\lambda_{\max}$ ~404 nm, could be located. An isosbestic point at ~380 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 3310 \pm 75 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is

observed. The presence of an isosbestic point as well as the appearance of a new band, 404 nm (with the addition of crown ether), indicate that acridine interacts with 18-crownether-6. The stoichiometry of the complex was found to be 1 : 1. The equilibrium constants and other thermodynamic parameters of the complex are given in Table 1. The equilibrium constant for 18-crownether-6-acridine complex at 25° is $94 \pm 2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and the molar extinction coefficient is $3846 \pm 145 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which decreases with the increase of temperature. The enthalpy of the complex formation is $-35.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ which is unusually high. Here it may be noted that in literature such cases are reported. The entropy change is small and negative and this indicates that the complex is enthalpy-controlled rather than entropy-controlled.

15-Crownether-5-acridine complex :

On the addition of 15-crown-5 to acridine, the absorbance of $\lambda_{\max}$ 355 nm increases whereas the band position is unaffected. From the differential spectra, a new band, CT band could be located ~405 nm. Moreover, the appearance of an isosbestic point at 380 nm ($\epsilon = 3332 \pm 133 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) confirms the complex formation between acridine and crownether. Equilibrium constants and other thermodynamic parameters of the complexes are summarized in Table 1. The ΔG° value was found to be very small, whereas, ΔH° is reasonably high (even though ΔG° and ΔH° go in parallel, it is not the case always). The complexation is found to be enthalpy-controlled.

12-Crownether-4-acridine complex :

On the addition of 12-crownether-4 to APB, the absorbance of acridine at 310–360 nm increases. A charge transfer band was observed at 405 nm whose absorbance increases with the increases in concentration of crown ether. An isosbestic point was observed at 380 nm ($\epsilon = 3142 \pm 124 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Equilibrium constants at various temperatures were determined and the results are included in Table 1. From the values of K and ΔG° , it appears that the complex formed between 12-crownether-4 and acridine is very weak. The entropy value in the present case is slightly higher and this indicates the contribution of entropy in formation of the complex is not negligible. From the present investigation, it is evident that the stability of acridine-crownether complexes vary in the order : 18-crownether-6-acridine > 15-crownether-5-acridine > 12-crownether-4-acridine.

18-Crownether-6-safranin-T complex :

The electronic absorption spectrum of safranin-T consists of three bands at 249, 276 and 520 nm. From the difference in absorption of safranin-T with and without 18-

crownether-6, a new band could be located at ~524 nm which can be ascribed as molecular adduct band. (The uncertainty in the λ_{CT} is high). A sharp isosbestic point was observed at 500 nm ($\epsilon_{iso} = 15830 \pm 126 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

The stoichiometry of the complex formed was 1 : 1. The equilibrium constant and other thermodynamic parameters for the complex formation were determined following the procedure mentioned earlier and the values are included in Table 1. The molar extinction coefficient of the complex obtained by separating K_ϵ was found to be low ($\epsilon_{CT} = 6666 \pm 175 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The enthalpy, free energy and entropy changes are very small and negative. The low values of ΔG° and ΔH° indicate that the host-guest (18-crownether-6–SFT) complex is weak. The small and negative entropy indicates that probably the complexation is enthalpy-controlled.

15-Crownether-5-safranin-T complex :

On the addition of 15-crownether-5, the absorbance of safranin-T increases and this increase is dependent on the concentration of crownether. From the difference of absorbance of SFT with and without crownether, a new band with $\lambda_{max} = 534 \text{ nm}$ could be observed which is due to the host-guest complex of 15-crownether-5–SFT. An isosbestic point at 500 nm ($\epsilon_{iso} = 15784 \pm 115 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was observed. The equilibrium constants and other thermodynamic parameters of the complex formation are included in Table 1. The equilibrium constant is very moderate. The molar extinction coefficient of the complex ϵ_{CT} is obtained by separating K from K_ϵ and was found to be $\sim 5000 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The enthalpy, free energy and entropy changes are small and negative and these indicate that the complex formed is very weak.

12-Crownether-4-safranin-T complex :

On the addition of 12-crownether-4, the absorption of SFT (λ_{max}) has slightly increased but the increase does not seem to be proportional to the concentration of crown ether. A new band at 528 nm was detected, which can be due to the inclusion of SFT into the cavity of 12-crownether-4. An isosbestic point at 553 nm (with less certainty) was located. As the increase in absorbance of the mixed system (compared to the free systems) was not much, it was not possible to determine the stoichiometry of 12-crownether-4–SFT system and for determination of the equilibrium constants and thermodynamic parameters, it was assumed that the host-guest complex formed is 1 : 1. The calculated equilibrium constants and other thermodynamic parameters are given in the Table 1.

From the present investigation, it is evident that SFT interacts with 18-crownether-6, 15-crownether-5 and 12-

crownether-4, and the interaction is very weak. The relative strengths of the complexes vary in the order : 18-crownether-6-safranin-T > 15-crownether-5-safranin-T > 12-crownether-4-safranin-T.

18-Crownether-6-azurene-A complex :

Azurene-A has absorption bands at 243 ± 2 ($\epsilon = 9600 \pm 152$), 288 ± 1 ($\epsilon = 24035 \pm 131$) and $632 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ ($\epsilon = 31458 \pm 148 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (lit. $\lambda_{max} = 632 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon_{max} = 33500 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a shoulder appears at $\sim 320 \text{ nm}$. The 632 nm band can be ascribed to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition. Addition of crown ether increases the absorbance of azurene-A. From the difference in absorption of azurene-A, with and without 18-crownether-6, a new band of the complex (host-guest) could be located with $\lambda_{max} \sim 634 \text{ nm}$. The presence of an isosbestic point at $\sim 603 \text{ nm}$ supports the evidence of the presence of 18-crownether-6-azurene-A complex. The stoichiometry of the complex is 1 : 1. The equilibrium constants and other thermodynamic parameters of the complex are given in Table 1. The entropy and free energy were found to be small and negative.

18-Crownether-6-azurene-B complex :

The electronic spectra of azurene-B is similar to that of azurene-A, azurene-B has absorption bands at 646, 290 and 245 nm; the slight red-shift in all the bands (compared to those azurene-A) may be due to the presence of two more CH_3 groups in azurene-B. Concentration independence of ϵ and λ of azurene-B indicates that azurene-B has not dimerized within the experimental range of concentration of the dye (10^{-6} to 10^{-5} M). On addition of crown ether, the absorbance of azurene-B in the visible region ($\lambda_{max} 636 \text{ nm}$) increases. The increased intensity of this band is temperature-dependent and is reversible. An isosbestic point ($\sim 610 \text{ nm}$) was also observed. The molar extinction coefficient is very low.

18-Crownether-6-azurene-C complex :

Azurene-C has absorption maxima at 612 ± 1 ($\epsilon = 33024 \pm 135$), 285 ± 1 ($\epsilon = 24611 \pm 127$) and $241 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ ($\epsilon = 8472 \pm 85 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in addition to a shoulder at $\sim 320 \text{ nm}$. On the addition of 18-crownether-6 to azurene-C, we could locate a new band with λ_{max} at 618 nm. An isosbestic point at 550 nm was detected. The equilibrium constants were determined and the results are summarized in Table 1. The ΔG° and ΔS° values are small and negative whereas ΔH° is negative but not that small. The stability of the complexes seems to vary in the order : azurene-C-18-crownether-6 > azurene-A-18-crownether-6.

Azures are cationic dyes and in water they are solvated. However, the solvation depends on the structure of

the dyes. When these solvated cations approach the crown ether, the solvation shall be stripped off from the dye molecule and then the ion-dipole interaction will take place. In the case of azurene-B, the bulky side groups substituted on the main ring may not fit properly in the crown ether as the hole size of the crown ether will determine how far the cation can protrude from the plane of the crown ether (steric hindrance). In addition, it may not be able to form proper sandwich type complex due to which the interaction between 18-crown ether-6 and azurene-B may be very weak. The other reason for weak interaction could be the strong interaction of azurene-B with solvent which may decrease the binding capability with crownether. Azurene-C has less crowded substituent, and this structure may favour a better fitting into the cavity of ion forming sandwich type complex. The enthalpies of complex formation of azurenes with 18-crownether-6 are negative whereas the entropy changes are small and negative, and from these data one can infer that the interaction between 18-crownether-6 and azurenes is strong and they are enthalpy-controlled.

15-Crownether-5-azurene-A complex :

With the addition of 15-crownether-5, the absorption of azurene-A is slightly enhanced. A new band located at $\lambda_{\max}$ 637 nm indicates the presence of the inclusion complex of crown ether with azurene-A. An isosbestic point was observed at 555 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 8520 \pm 108 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Equilibrium constants at various temperatures were determined and the calculated thermodynamic parameters are summarized in the Table 1. The enthalpy change for the complexation is quite high whereas the entropy change is small and negative, and these indicate that the complex formation is enthalpy-controlled.

15-Crownether-5-azurene-B complex :

On the addition of 15-crownether-5, the absorbance of azurene-B is increased, however, the increase is not much. A new band with maximum at 662 nm could be located. An isosbestic point was observed at 557 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 8632 \pm 103 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The equilibrium constants and other thermodynamic parameters were calculated and they are given in Table 1. The low value of equilibrium constant as well as molar extinction coefficient show that the interaction between 15-crownether-5 and azurene-B is very weak. The weak interaction between 15-crownether-5 and azurene-B may be ascribed due to the bulky substituents on azurene-B which may prevent the formation of inclusion complex.

15-Crownether-5-azurene-C complex :

The absorption spectra of azurene-C with various concentrations of 15-crownether-5 show that the addition of 15-crownether-5 increases the absorbance of azurene-C and

the increase in absorbance depends on the amount of crown ether added. A new band at 620 nm was located. The presence of an isosbestic point ($\lambda_{\text{iso}} = 650 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon_{\text{iso}} = 6627 \pm 128 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) supports the evidence of presence of 15-crownether-5-azurene-C complex. The equilibrium constant and other thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1. The equilibrium constant and enthalpy of complex formation indicate that the interaction is neither too weak nor too strong.

When azurene, a cationic dye, is added to the crown ethers, it is expected that azurene either enters into the cavity of crown ether forming host-guest complex or it sits on the plane of the crown forming sandwich type of molecular adduct. The crown ethers have only oxygen atoms which are not good donors. Even though azurenes are cationic dyes, as they have large number of π and n electrons, they are poor electron-acceptors. Therefore, the interaction between crown ether and azurene is not expected to be strong and that is what has been observed. Amongst azurenes, azurene-B has maximum number of bulky groups (and hence maximum steric hindrance in the complex formation). So, azurene-B may not fit properly in the crown ether cavity/ may not be able to form proper sandwich type adducts. Therefore, the interaction between crown ethers (whether it is 18-crownether-6 or 15-crownether-5) and azurene-B is expected to be weakest, whereas azurene-C (which is having least steric hindrance) can interact more effectively with the crown ethers and form relatively strong complexes.

Amongst the crown ethers, 18-crownether-6 has the large cavity compared to 15-crownether-5. In host-guest systems, the guest molecules, e.g. azurenes in the present case, enter into the cavity of the host molecule, provided the geometry (diameter) of the guest molecules is such that they can be properly accommodated in the host cavities. So, it appears that the size/geometry of the azurenes are such that they form stronger complexes with 18-crownether-6, which has larger cavity compared to 15-crownether-5.

From the present investigations, it is evident that 18-crownether-5 and 15-crownether-5 interact with azurene-A, azurene-B and azurene-C and form host-guest complexes. 18-Crownether-6 seems to be a better host compared to 15-crownether-5. On the basis of enthalpy changes, it appears that the complexes are weak and the complexation is enthalpy-controlled. The size of the host and the geometry of the guest seem to play a crucial role in complexation. The interaction between azurenes and crown ether varies in the order : 18-crownether-6-azurene-C > 18-crownether-6-azurene-A > 18-crownether-6-azurene-B, and the same trend is observed when 15-crownether-5 is used as the host.

Experimental

Stock solutions ($\sim 10^{-4}$ M) of the dyes (guests) were prepared in double-distilled water. Further dilutions ($\sim 10^{-5}$ M) were made for recording the electronic absorption spectra of the dyes. Required amounts of the crown ethers were added to the solution (10 ml) of the dyes so that the final concentrations of the hosts (with the fixed concentrations of dye) were $\sim 10^{-1}$ to 10^{-4} M. The spectra were recorded with Hitachi-33 NIR-UV-VIS and Beckman DU-650 spectrophotometers fitted with matched pair of 1 cm cells. Constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) was maintained by circulating water.

Equilibrium constants were calculated using modified Benesi-Hildebrand equation⁷ as well as of Nagakura's equation⁸. Enthalpy was calculated by plotting $\log K_\epsilon$ vs $1/T$. The free energy and entropy changes were calculated by the usual procedure.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. K. Ismail, Head, Department of Chemistry, NEHU, for facilities. One of the authors (V. J.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for partial financial support.

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